

MOTHERHEAT ALERT: AN EARLY WARNING SYSTEM APP FOR PREGNANT AND POSTPARTUM WOMEN, INFANTS AND HEALTH WORKERS

Deliverable 3.4

MotherHeat Alert: An early warning system app for pregnant and postpartum women, infants and health workers

HIGH HORIZONS – D3.4

[GRANT NO. 101057843]

Deliverable Information	
Title	MotherHeat Alert: An early warning system app for pregnant and postpartum women, infants and health workers* *Original title: Developed ClimApp EWS prototype
Deliverable number	D3.4
WP number	3
Author(s)	Chuansi Gao, Günter Alce, Clara Heil (ULUND); Koen van der Sanden, Boris Kingma (TNO)
Lead beneficiary	ULUND & TNO
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Due date	31 March 2024 (version 1) 31 August 2025 (version 2)

History of Changes	
Version 0.1	Draft, 18 March 2024
Version 1.0	Report with integration of internal comments, 28 March 2024
Version 2.0	Updated version with modifications made to the prototype till start of implementation in South Africa in November 2024, in Sweden and Zimbabwe in June 2025. Modifications include app name and logo, extra screens, participants profiles and messages and the research questions, 29 August 2025

This document is issued within the frame and for the purpose of the HIGH Horizons project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Framework Programme under Grant Agreement number 101057843. Project partner LSHTM is funded by UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478. The opinions expressed and arguments employed herein do not necessarily reflect the official views of the European Commission or UKRI. The dissemination of this document reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission and UKRI are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. This deliverable is subject to final acceptance by the European Commission. This document and its content are the property of the HIGH Horizons Consortium. The content of all or parts of this document can be used and distributed provided that the HIGH Horizons project and the document are properly referenced. Each HIGH Horizons Partner may use this document in conformity with the HIGH Horizons Consortium Grant Agreement provisions.

Table of Contents

List of tables	4
List of figures	4
Abbreviations.....	4
1 Introduction.....	5
1.1 Purpose of the document.....	5
1.2 Relation to other project work	6
2 Background	6
3 User interface.....	7
3.1 Home screen.....	9
3.2 User profile screen	12
3.3 Research screen.....	14
3.4 About screen.....	15
4 Software Architecture.....	16
4.1 Application architecture.....	16
4.2 Warning and advice decisions.....	18
5 Conclusion	19
6 References	22
7 Annexes.....	23
7.1 Annex A: User manual.....	23
7.2 Annex B: Guidance document for Android phones.....	35
7.3 Annex C: Guidance document for iPhones	38

List of tables

Table 1. Profile information implemented in the beta version of the MotherHeat Alert app..... 13

List of figures

Figure 1. MotherHeat Alert app icon 7

Figure 2. MotherHeat Alert interface screens 8

Figure 3. MotherHeat Alert home screen with labelled buttons 9

Figure 4. MotherHeat Alert onboarding pages in order from left to right 10

Figure 5. MotherHeat Alert pop-up windows 11

Figure 6. MotherHeat Alert about screen 15

Figure 7. Schematic depiction of MotherHeat Alert app architecture 16

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
BMI	Body mass index
EU	European Union
EWS	Early Warning System
GPS	Global Positioning System
MCH	Maternal and child health
SOP	Standard operating procedure
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
ULUND	Lund University
UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable report presents the prototype of the MotherHeat Alert, the personalised and context-specific early warning system (EWS) that is being tested by pregnant and postpartum women, health workers and community health workers in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe.

The prototype was developed by HIGH Horizons partner Lund University (ULUND) and subcontractor TNO, the Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research. MotherHeat Alert is a smartphone app adapted from ClimApp that was developed and applied in a previous, EU-funded project¹. ClimApp integrates comprehensive heat stress indices and individual factors to provide personalised warnings and advice when facing extreme heat and cold events. The current version of ClimApp was adapted to vulnerable groups of pregnant and postpartum women, infants and health workers taking care of them. The prototype of MotherHeat Alert was therefore provisionally called ClimApp-MCH, thereby referring to maternal and child health (MCH).

MotherHeat Alert aims to play a role as a tool to make heat warnings and advice more accessible for everyone and make people aware of heat health risks and appropriate behaviour to reduce heat effects during periods with high ambient temperatures.

This report details the beta version (Android 1.1.2, iOS 1.0.0 (20)) of the MotherHeat Alert application² for internal testing and evaluation by recruited participants within the HIGH Horizons project. The standard operating procedures

¹ ClimApp received an award from the World Meteorological Organization for innovation and promotion of the use of weather and climate information in December 2020.

² A demonstration video of the MotherHeat Alert prototype can be watched on <https://youtu.be/8FgklpK1J0Y>.

(SOP) for the MotherHeat Alert provide users with an overview of the most common interactions between user and the MotherHeat Alert app (Annex A).

The application's prototype will be further finetuned based on input from the HIGH Horizons consortium partners and feedback from the recruited participants. Therefore, the final release might look and function differently than described in this document. The possibility of final public release of the MotherHeat Alert will be further investigated in terms of ethical issues and resources to maintain operation.

1.2 Relation to other project work

This deliverable is building on and feeding into other deliverables, including:

- D3.3 - Predictive EWS thresholds (February 2024) [1];
- D3.5 - Report on PhotoVoice sub-study, and the locally-adapted and optimised messaging (February 2024) [2];
- D4.6 - 600 women successfully used EWS (due March 2026)
- D4.7 - 60 health workers successfully used EWS (due December 2025)
- D5.2 - Protocol for EWS evaluation (February 2024) [3];
- D5.3 - Evaluation of experiences and effectiveness of EWS and messages targeting pregnant and postpartum women, and infants (due March 2026).

2 Background

Climate change is causing more extreme weather around the globe [4]. Hot weather occurs more often and is more intense. As a result, heat stress is increasingly common and more severe. While heat stress poses health risks to everyone, certain vulnerable populations are especially at risk. Pregnant and postpartum women, infants and young children comprise some of these vulnerable groups.

This report is focused on developing an early heat warning system. The system should be able to send timely and appropriate warnings, information and advice to individuals and health workers regarding heat stress, resulting in improved response capacity and risk knowledge. The early warning system is a smartphone application, based on the previously developed ClimApp concept [5, 6], a personalised smartphone app that can be used to assess heat and cold stress, provide warnings and recommendations. The advantage of using a smartphone app is the widespread availability, personalisation, two-way interactions between the app and the user, ease-of-use and ability to connect to the internet for the latest updates and most relevant local weather information.

The developed EWS application is named MotherHeat Alert because the app focuses on pregnant and postpartum women, infants and young children and provides individualised heat stress predictions, information and advice to the user. It makes use of an internet connection to retrieve the latest current local weather and to issue forecasts. It uses the weather data to calculate various heat stress indices such as the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) [7, 8] which gives a more appropriate and detailed insight into the heat stress influenced by all thermal climate factors experienced by the human body, beyond only air temperature.

3 User interface

The icon of the EWS MotherHeat Alert app was designed to inclusively target the vulnerable group users in the three study countries: South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe (Figure 1).

Figure 1. MotherHeat Alert app icon

The user interface of the EWS app currently consists of four screens: the home screen, the profile screen, the research screen and the about screen (Figure 2).

Figure 2. MotherHeat Alert interface screens

Note: From left to right: the home screen, the profile screen (top panel), the research screen and about screen (under panel).

Switching between the screens can be done easily by clicking the respective button on the navigation bar which constantly appears at the bottom of the screen. The user interface is in English by default but will automatically switch to the preferred language of the smartphone if that language is available in the MotherHeat Alert database. Three local languages (i.e. Northern Sotho, Swedish and Shona) are incorporated into the app.

The application is built on the Flutter framework in the Dart programming language. This framework provides a native look and feel to the application, integrating well with all standard smartphone functionality.

3.1 Home screen

The home screen contains all the essential information for the user of the app. It shows the location, the present weather conditions (current air temperature and UTCI), warnings that are currently active for today and warnings for the future (next 2 and 7 days). All this information is automatically retrieved or calculated if an internet connection is available. The local weather information is retrieved via secure servers at TNO by sharing the user's latitude and longitude (determined through GPS).

The user can interact with the home screen in various ways. The clickable or touchable areas (buttons) are labelled in Figure 3. The function of the buttons is, in order:

[1] The information button opens the onboarding pages, which gives information about the application and allows the user to fill in their profile information such as country, pregnancy month, age, etc. The onboarding pages are shown in

Figure 3. MotherHeat Alert home screen with labelled buttons

Note: See text for detailed functionality of each button.

Figure 4. By default, these pages are also shown when someone opens the application for the first time.

Figure 4. MotherHeat Alert onboarding pages in order from left to right

[2] The refresh button updates the weather data to the latest local weather now- and forecast. If the user has manually input weather data, pressing the refresh button will switch back to automatic weather forecast data.

[3] Clicking the location or weather information will open a new window which allows for manual weather and air pollution input. The manual weather input window is shown in Figure 5 (left). By default, the values are auto filled with the latest weather data update – which is the weather now- and forecast if weather data is not entered manually before. The user can easily see whether the weather forecast or manual weather data is used by inspecting the letter just after the location. It shows the for manual. The manual weather input does not support a forecast, only a nowcast. When manually entering weather data, the input is saved instantly without pressing a button. To exit the manual input window, the user needs to press “Close” or anywhere

outside of the active window. To return to automatic weather input, click on the name of the location for example "Lund", the icon ↻ will appear again. The manual weather input functionality is designed to provide the possibility to input locally measured micro thermal conditions, for example indoor thermal environments in health facilities, which can be quite different from prevailing outdoor weather.

[4] When UTCI exceeds thresholds, the app provides heat warning "High Heat Expected". Then "Messages" for actions to reduce heat risks will be shown in several categories such as stay hydrated, cool body, etc.

[5] The profile of the user can be selected from a drop-down list (pregnant woman; mother; infant; healthcare worker; community health worker).

Clicking a category of messages will open a new window with a more detailed description of the advised action, as shown in Figure 5 (right).

Figure 5. MotherHeat Alert pop-up windows

Note: The manual weather input (left) and the detailed advice when clicking a message category (right). The advice messages can be further shared via SMS, WhatsApp, email, etc.

The window contains a share button. The share button opens the native Android or iOS share menu, which allows for easy copying of the text or directly sending it via SMS, WhatsApp, email, etc.

The SOP on how to install and use the MotherHeat Alert app in Android and iOS versions are available in Annex A. For the online recruitment in Sweden, a guidance document with simplified instructions on how to install the MotherHeat Alert app in Android and iOS versions is shared online and linked to the information for participants during recruitment (Annex B and C respectively).

3.2 User profile screen

The profile screen contains all information about the user themselves. This information is mainly used to communicate the appropriate heat warnings and advice for which vulnerable user group (pregnant woman, mother, infants, health worker, community health worker).

The profile screen is built up from six questions about:

1. the county the user is in (South Africa, Sweden, Zimbabwe and Other),
2. the group the user belongs to (pregnant woman, mother, infant, healthcare worker, community healthcare worker),
3. the language (English or a local language for each of the three countries) for warnings, and advice messages.
4. the month of pregnancy (only for pregnant woman user profile).
5. first pregnancy or not (only for pregnant woman user profile).
6. age.

The input is either in the form of single or multiple selectable options or in the form of a question with a number response (e.g. what is the user's age?). Specific answers can also trigger additional questions to appear, for example if a user indicates to be a pregnant woman, the question regarding which trimester they are in will then appear. It will not show if the user is not a pregnant woman.

At the bottom of the above “mandatory” questions is a section of optional questions (body height, weight, acclimatisation to heat). The mandatory information such as user group is required to use the application, the user profile information and associated heat threshold is used to personalise in-app decisions such as whether the heat level threshold is exceeded for a specific user group, whether a heat risk warning is triggered, what advice messages to provide, etc. Optional information is not required for the application to function or personalise the warnings. The purpose of the optional information is that it will be sent to the server when the user submits answers to the research questions on the research screen and can provide context to the user’s answers, possibly leading to new insights based on analysis of the data submitted by participants.

The user profile information currently implemented are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Profile information implemented in the beta version of the MotherHeat Alert app

Question	Mandatory	Type	Options	Requirement
Which country are you located in?	Yes	Single selection	South Africa; Sweden; Zimbabwe; Other	
Which groups do you belong to?	Yes	Multiple selection	Pregnant woman; Mother; Infant; Healthcare worker; Community healthcare worker	Community healthcare worker only available if country is Zimbabwe Healthcare worker only available if country is Zimbabwe or South Africa
Which language do you want to receive warnings?	Yes	Single selection	English; Northern Sotho; Swedish; Shona	
How long have you been pregnant?	Yes	Single selection	1-3 months; 4-6 months; 7-9 months	User is a pregnant woman
Is this your first pregnancy?	Yes	Single selection	Yes; No	User is a pregnant woman

Question	Mandatory	Type	Options	Requirement
What is your age?	Yes	Number input	-	-
What is your body height?	No	Number input		
What is your body weight?	No	Number input	-	-
Have you been in a warm environment for more than a week?	No	Single selection	Yes; No	-

3.3 Research screen

The research screen consists of questions and a corresponding answer field for each question (see below). The answer fields are text fields or drop-down list so the user may type freely (text and/or numbers) or select from the drop-down list. At the bottom of the research screen are the information for participants, consent form (for Swedish participants) and a button to submit the answers. When the consent form is ticked and this Submit Answers button is pressed, the answers to all questions are submitted to TNO servers. The submitted data also contains the current weather, the weather forecast, the user location, and user profile data loaded in the application. The data is only submitted once the submit button is pressed. Data is submitted in plain text to secure TNO servers.

Questions on the researcher screen are listed below:

- *What is your participant ID?*
- *Q1 Apart from completing this survey, did you access the MotherHeat Alert app in the past 7 days? Yes / No*
- *Q2 Was the message you received relevant for your situation? Yes / No*
- *Q3 Did you follow the advice provided? Yes / No*
- *Q4 On a scale of 1 to 5, please rate how easy you have found it to use the app. 1 (Very easy) / 2 (Easy) / 3 (Neutral) / 4 (Difficult) / 5 (Very difficult)*

- Q5 Thinking about the weather, how do you feel right now? 3 Hot / 2 Warm / 1 Slightly warm / 0 Neutral / -1 Slightly cool / -2 Cool / -3 Cold
- Q6 Please rate how comfortable the weather feels for you right now? 0 Comfortable / 1 Slightly uncomfortable / 2 Uncomfortable / 3 Very uncomfortable / 4 Extremely uncomfortable
- Q7 Please rate your current level of wetness due to sweating. 1 (Dry) / 2 (A little wet) / 3 (Wet) / 4 (Extremely wet)

3.4 About screen

The about screen (Figure 6) describes the purpose of the MotherHeat Alert app and highlights that the app is being tested. Reference is made to the HIGH Horizons project and its funders. Heat health risk information is added. Other sources including infographics and links to WHO Heat Health info, UNICEF tips on keeping safe in extreme heat, WHO Climate Change and Health are provided with the aim to increase user’s knowledge of heat health risks and recommendations to reduce the risks.

Figure 6. MotherHeat Alert about screen

4 Software Architecture

4.1 Application architecture

The application architecture is schematically depicted in Figure 7. The app is functional offline, for example when users input present weather data manually, the app will assess heat and health risks and provide warnings and advice when heat stress is above the threshold level. Several functions however do require internet connection to function: forecasted weather data, alerts with heat warnings, updating application information (warning rules and advice messages), and all functionality on the research page.

Figure 7. Schematic depiction of MotherHeat Alert app architecture

At the centre of the connection to the internet is the *TNO server*. The *TNO server* provides the application with *Application Information* which contains the heat warnings, advice messages, advice images, etc. Essentially all the rules for which warnings to deliver, when to show them and what the warnings indicate and look like. If no internet connection is available, the application simply uses the last known version of the *Application Information*. An initial version of the *Application Information* is included in the installed version of the application right out of the gate. This ensures that everything functions even if the phone is never connected to the internet when MotherHeat Alert is open.

The *TNO Server* also handles the weather and air pollution data requests. The user shares their location (latitude and longitude) with the TNO server, which then sends the required weather and air pollution information. The weather information is collected from the *OpenWeatherMaps*. The weather and location data is stored in the *User Database*, containing local data that is only available to the phone itself. The *Profile Screen* also uses the database to store the user's profile data.

When the *Home Screen* is opened the application takes information from the *Application Information* and the *User Database* to apply the rulesets of warnings and advice to the currently stored weather and user information. These calculations are done locally, so they work even without internet connectivity. The resulting warnings and advice are shown on the home screen. The *TNO Server* is also able to send a command to all phones with MotherHeat Alert installed to trigger the warning and advice decision application in the background. If the background calculation results in a warning, the user is alerted by a notification. The background calculation triggered notification is sent once a day in the morning.

The *Research Screen* communicates directly with the *TNO Server*. When it is opened the questions are taken from the server and when answers are submitted it sends all the questions, answers and user data to the *TNO Server* where it is stored for development purposes, from which the data is transferred to ULUND and the consortium for data analysis and report.

4.2 Warning and advice decisions

Possibly the most important part of the application is the decision-making process of which heat risk warnings to show and when to show them. The ruleset, e.g. heat thresholds for this is stored in the *Application Information*, which details warning triggers and consequences. The decision-making process then applies these rules to the data from the *User Database* to show the relevant warnings and advice messages for that user in those conditions.

A trigger is defined as a parameter, an operator and a value. The available parameters are all stored in the *User Database* and consist mostly of weather, air pollution and user profile data. An operator is a standard operator such as equals, greater than, less than or equal to, etc. The value functions as a check value such as a heat threshold which completes the equation. As an example, we can create the trigger: $UTCI_{max} \geq 27.3 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. When the maximum UTCI is 27.3 °C or higher, this trigger requirement is met and so the associated consequence will be triggered. A consequence consists of two parts: an alert (warning) which can be shown as a notification outside the application and action messages which are shown in the application and provides more details and advice.

It is possible to define multiple triggers for a single consequence. In that case all triggers need to be triggered for the consequence to happen. Different consequences can also show the same warning. In that case the warning is shown whenever either consequence occurs. The same advice message is never shown multiple times, even if multiple consequences trigger it.

In version (Android 1.1.2, iOS 1.0.0) of MotherHeat Alert, heat risk triggers are based on the UTCI, which is derived from weather data. The UTCI was chosen because it is possible to calculate using weather data and it provides more insight into heat stress than only using air temperature. UTCI takes into account all thermal climate variables. Clothing and activity level are integrated into UTCI by default. This makes it easier to use for end-users as they need to answer easier and fewer questions and can still receive comprehensive advice.

It is important to note that the ruleset (triggers and consequences, heat thresholds) and advice messages are specifically developed for internal testing and evaluation in the three countries and the targeted user groups. The first public version of the application was released after the consortium had reached consensus on ethics, research functionality, maintenance of the app operation, etc. Heat thresholds and messages may still need to be revised if made available for other countries. It is the HIGH Horizons consortium that is responsible for the ruleset, including triggers and consequences. The consortium will also decide on the exact warnings and advice messages; both the text and any infographics associated with them. The approach for developing the messages is explained in deliverable D3.5 - Report on PhotoVoice sub-study, and the locally-adapted and optimised messaging [2]. The heat health early warning thresholds are included in deliverable D3.3 - Report on predictive heat warning thresholds [1]. The implementation and evaluation of the MotherHeat Alert will be described in forthcoming deliverables.

5 Conclusion

This report details the design and development of MotherHeat Alert (beta version android 1.1.2, iOS 1.0.0), led by ULUND and incorporation with partners in the HIGH Horizons project. The technical development of the application is mainly carried out by TNO. MotherHeat Alert functions as an early heat warning system

for pregnant and postpartum women, infants, health workers, and community health workers who take care of them, such as in health facilities and communities. The application is focussed specifically on these vulnerable populations.

In this beta version of the application the focus lies on the correct configuration of the user interface and the underlying architecture. The user interface focuses on simplicity and ease of use. It only consists of four screens: the home screen, the profile screen, the research screen and the about screen. The home screen shows all weather information, including any heat stress warnings and advice messages. The profile screen is used to specify the user data such as user group, preferred language, and age. The research screen is used for research purposes; users can answer a set of questions to provide feedback to the project consortium. The about screen presents heat health risk information, the HIGH Horizons project, sources and links.

The underlying architecture of the application has been set up. The application is designed such that it functions offline by storing weather data and heat stress trigger information offline once it has been pulled from the internet once. This also allows for evaluating manual input weather conditions, potentially making the application more suitable for indoor use.

An important part of the application architecture is the TNO server. It provides the ruleset, including the triggers, heat stress warnings and advice, forming the blueprint of which warnings to deliver and when to display them. The TNO server also uses the weather and air pollution data for the user's location using the OpenWeatherMaps API and forwards it to the application. The TNO server also sends background calculation triggers to the application every day in order to use any heat warnings for that specific day or in the forecast. Finally, the TNO server stores the research questions and answers and forwards the data to ULUND, where it will be analysed to evaluate the usability, uptake and effectiveness of the

app, and to analyse the relationship between the heat exposure and health response of the users. The results can be used to improve warning thresholds, which also will be assessed.

Although the user interface and architecture of the MotherHeat Alert early warning system have been set up, there is substantial work in deciding the exact triggers and threshold levels (when to show warnings) and what the consequence of a triggered warning looks like (which warnings to show and what advice to give). The HIGH Horizons consortium analysed these based on information from literature studies, compiling a systematic review [9], through heat health data analyses [10] and knowledge of experts.³ Internal pilot tests of the app were conducted before it was used by the target users in the implementation and evaluation phase of the project.

The version (android 1.1.2 and iOS 1.0.0) application prototype is available to consortium members and recruited participants in the three countries in the Google Play Store and App Store test environment. In future iterations based on feedback from the recruited participants, MotherHeat Alert may be made publicly available in Android and iOS versions for a larger audience.

³ The HIGH Horizons website ([Publications – HIGH Horizons](#)) has an overview of all publications and project deliverables objective. Deliverables which have been approved are also uploaded in the Zenodo community of HIGH Horizons ([Search HIGH Horizons](#)).

6 References

- [1] Gao C, Heil C, Portela A, Brimicombe C, HIGH Horizons Study Group. HIGH Horizons - Report on predictive heat warning thresholds. Zenodo; 2024 Jul. <https://zenodo.org/records/12649827>
- [2] Lange I, Solarin I, Scorgie F, Machingura F, Roos N, HIGH Horizons Study Group. HIGH Horizons - Report on the development of messages for pregnant and post-partum women for the early warning system ClimApp-MCH. Zenodo; 2024 Jul. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12730928>
- [3] Gao C, Heil C, Eggeling J, Alce G, Luchters S, Machingura F, et al. HIGH Horizons - Protocol for testing of the EWS among pregnant and postpartum women, young children and health workers. Zenodo; 2024 Aug. <https://zenodo.org/records/13149904>
- [4] IPCC: Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge University Press (2021)
- [5] Kingma BRM, Steenhoff H, Toftum J, Daanen HAM, Folkerts MA, Gerrett N, Gao C, Kuklane K, Petersson J, Halder A, Zuurbier M, Garland SW, Nybo L. Climapp—integrating personal factors with weather forecasts for individualised warning and guidance on thermal stress. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health.* 18, 1–26 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182111317>
- [6] Lund University: ClimApp, <https://apps.apple.com/nl/app/climapp/id1458460604> (2021)
- [7] Bröde P, Fiala D, Błażejczyk K, Holmér I, Jendritzky G, Kampmann B, Tinz B, Havenith G. Deriving the operational procedure for the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI). *Int. J. Biometeorol.* 56, 481–494 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-011-0454-1>
- [8] Jendritzky G, de Dear R, Havenith G. UTCI-Why another thermal index? *Int. J. Biometeorol.* 56, 421–428 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-011-0513-7>
- [9] Lakhoo DP, Brink N, Radebe L, Craig MH, Pham MD, Haghighi MM, Wise A, Solarin I, Luchters S, Maimela G, Chersich MF; Heat-Health Study Group; HIGH Horizons Study Group. A systematic review and meta-analysis of heat exposure impacts on maternal, foetal and neonatal health. *Nat Med.* 2024. [doi: 10.1038/s41591-024-03395-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-024-03395-8)
- [10] Brimicombe C, Wieser K, Monthaler T, Otto IM, Part C, Jackson D, et al. HIGH Horizons - Heat-health analysis report from Greek, Italian, Swedish and African data 1. Zenodo; 2024 Jul. <https://zenodo.org/records/12683547>

7 Annexes

7.1 Annex A: User manual

For the implementing teams in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe, a user manual with the standard operating procedures on how best to implement the MotherHeat Alert app was prepared.

Standard operation procedure MotherHeat Alert

Contents

Introduction	3
Onboarding function.....	4
Home screen	6
Messages.....	8
Navigation panel	9
Research function	10
About the app	11

Introduction

This document is intended to provide users with an overview of the most common interactions between user and the MotherHeat Alert app.

For downloading and installing the app in Android version, watch the short video on the SharePoint [Internal App Sharing Instructions.mp4](#) , then use your mobile phone and click on the internal link, follow the instructions in the video to turn on Internal App Sharing of your phone settings. You are now able to install the app.

For iPhone users, you install a free TestFlight app from AppStore, then use your phone to click on <https://testflight.apple.com/join/8UvP8gPA> to install MotherHeat Alert app in iOS version.

Onboarding function

When the user opens the MotherHeat Alert app for the first time, they will be greeted by the onboarding function (Figure 1a-c). The first screen (1a) presents the logo of the app, the user can choose to move to the next screen by swiping right or pressing the blue right-facing arrow in the bottom right corner or skipping the onboarding function. The second screen (1b) presents the user with a basic presentation of the app and similar navigation as previous screen with the possibility to return by swiping left. The third screen (1c) allows the user to select basic information such as:

- Country, the country the person is in as this affects language options
- Group, this affects the advice that will be presented to the user, multiple groups can be selected as the app can be used for the intent of providing messages to different groups
 - Pregnant woman
 - Mother
 - Infant
 - Healthcare worker (for users in South Africa)
 - Facility Healthcare workers (for users in Zimbabwe)
 - Community Healthcare workers (for users in Zimbabwe)
- Language
- Age
- Optional information, a dropdown menu that can be accessed by clicking on the downfacing arrowhead.

Figure 1. 1a (left): The first screen of the app, the MotherHeat Alert logo. 1b (middle): The second screen of the onboarding function, which provides brief information about the purpose of the app. 1c (right): The basic information screen where the user can input details about themselves.

An example of selected information is visualized in Figure 2a. The group “Pregnant woman” allows for further detailing how long the user has been pregnant. In Figure 2b, the “Optional information” (mentioned in 1c) is accessed, and additional information can be entered, this will improve the accuracy of the advice provided by the app.

Which country are you located in?
South Africa

Which groups do you belong to?
Pregnant woman

Which language do you want to receive warnings in?
English

How long have you been you pregnant?
4-6 Months

Is this your first pregnancy?
No

What is your age in years?
Enter your age
35

No

What is your age in years?
Enter your age
35

Optional Information

What is your height in cm?
What is your height in cm?
175

What is your weight in kg?
What is your weight in kg?
77

Have you been in a warm environment for more than a week?
Yes

Done

Done

Figure 2. 2a (left): Example of a user selecting representable information from the last screen in the onboarding function. 2b (right): The dropdown menu “Optional Information” has been pressed and anthropometric data can be input as well as information about their acclimatization status. Being exposed to a warm environment for more than a week promotes physiological responses that assists the individual to cope in the heat, such as improved automatic sweat responses.

When entering the desired information on the last screen of the onboarding function, the user can press “Done” in the bottom right corner and continue to the Home screen.

Home screen

When the onboarding experience is finished, and when the user opens up the app in the next time, they are greeted by the Home screen. The Home screen has 5 interactable buttons which are highlighted by colored boxes and numbers in Figure 3:

1. Update weather forecast. Below this button, a line of text details from when (GMT/UTC time) the active weather forecast is collected. This forecast should be updated before interpreting warnings and messages.
2. If the weather forecast is not representative of the local weather, the user can press on or near the forecast information to directly enter weather data. An example of pressing this button is seen in Figure 4a. If the weather is manually entered, the update icon is changed to two encircling arrows struck by a line (see Figure 5a).
3. The user can select for which group the advice should be presented by pressing the button which is preset to "My Profile". An example of pressing the button is seen in Figure 4b.
4. When pressing on a message, additional information is presented to the user. In Figure 3, no messages are present, which means low or no heat health risk, therefore no messages and recommendations. If there is heat and health risk, See Figure 5a-c for examples, multiple messages will be present, and the user can scroll down on this screen to see all messages.

By pressing the encircled "i" on the upper right corner, the user is returned to the onboarding function. This button is available on all screens in the app except inside the onboarding function.

The user has the possibility to directly input the weather forecast or measured data (Figure 4a), this can be beneficial in situations where the weather forecast is not accurate for the user's local environment, for example if most of the area experience overcast (cloudy weather) but the user is experiencing very strong solar radiation (high black globe temperature) or if a shelter is removing the influence of wind or if the user stays in an indoor environment. If the person desires to get advice for a specific group, they can interact with button 3 in Figure 3 which yields the drop-down menu in Figure 4b.

Figure 3. The home screen presents information about the weather and relevant messages on how to cope with heat can be seen at the bottom of the screen if heat stress is expected.

Figure 4. 4a (left): The manual weather input is available if the user presses anywhere on or near the weather forecast information on the Home screen. 4b (right): If pressing the button for whom the user would like to see advice for, the user is prompted to select the desired group or groups from a dropdown list.

Messages

The messages and advice presented to the user are derived from an algorithm that takes into account the profile information provided by the user in the onboarding function, the weather forecast, heat health risk threshold, and the selected group. Based on this input, the app will present the user with meaningful advice and messages on how to cope with the heat. Examples of these messages can be seen in Figure 5a-c. In Figure 5a, a hot environment has been manually input (note the changed icon for updating weather forecast and missing text about when the weather was updated). By pressing the “Stay Hydrated” button, the user is presented with advice on how to handle this situation (5b). Additional details about the advice, in this case “Drink a cup of water every hour”, are obtained by pressing the face-down arrowhead which is highlighted in Figure 5b. The additional information is presented in Figure 5c and further explains the measures related to the advice.

Figure 5. 5a (left): The Home screen has active messages, advice for staying hydrated is available. 5b (middle): When the “Stay Hydrated” message has been selected, advice is presented, and further details are available if pressing the corresponding facedown arrowhead for each advice. 5c (right): The “Drink a cup of water every hour” advice has been selected for additional information, the advice can be shared as a text with external messaging systems by pressing the share icon.

Navigation panel

The bottom panel of the app (Figure 6) allows for navigation between the four different main screens of the app. The active screen will be highlighted by a **blue text** below the **blue icon**. The icons, from left to right, are:

- Home: House icon, where weather forecast and messages are interactable
- Profile: Head and shoulders icon, where the user can input their geographic, group, and anthropometric information. This is the same screen as the final screen in the onboarding function
- Research: Flask icon, here the user can provide feedback regarding the ease of use of the app, how comfortable the weather you feel, the relevance of the messages and advice, etc. See Figure 7a, b.
- About: Folder icon, information about the app can be found here, such as purpose and aim of the MotherHeat Alert app. See Figure 8.

Figure 6. The navigation panel is available at the bottom of the app screens except for the onboarding function. This navigation panel allows for navigation to the Home screen, the Profile information screen, the Research function screen, and the about the App screen.

Research function

The research function allows for the user to submit details regarding their experiences using the app and their perception of the weather in the form of a survey. The survey is completed by answering seven questions with text answers as well as with ratings of scales with sliders. To answer a question with text, press the text box to enable text input (Figure 7a). To answer a question with a slider, either press on the desired level or press and hold which allows for dragging the slider to the desired rating score (Figure 7b, mark 1). The sliders are typically defined with a low rating score to the left and high rating score to the right. The research function screen has several buttons, the user has the possibility to share their participant ID by pressing the share icon marked on Figure 7b (box highlighted with number 2). In order to submit the survey data, the user needs to accept that the data is shared with the High Horizons team for research purpose by checking the box on Figure 7b (box highlighted with number 3). When the box is checked, the survey results can be submitted by pressing the “Submit Answers” on Figure 7b (box highlighted with number 4).

Figure 7. 7a (left): The upper part of the Research function screen. The first question of the survey is a text box question regarding the participant ID. 7b (right): By scrolling down, additional questions are available and the possibility to submit the survey.

About the app

The About screen is available by pressing the far-right icon (“Folder icon”) on the navigation panel at the bottom of the screen.

The screen presents information about the app, the purpose of the app, and information about the HIGH Horizons project such as research focus and funding information.

Figure 8. The About screen presents general information about the app and its purpose.

7.2 Annex B: Guidance document for Android phones

Because of the online recruitment of the cohort in Sweden, a guidance document on how to download, install and use the MotherHeat Alert app was shared with implementers in Sweden. The instructions are also incorporated in the online recruitment for cohort participants. The guidance document is available for Android phones and iPhones (Annex C).

How to Download the MotherHeat Alert (v1.1.2) Using Android Phone

Follow these steps to install the app from the following link:

<https://play.google.com/apps/test/RQJb-fWZvac/ahAO29uNRfcTdNQ4UplopGTq5-2COe7FL4pT63odlVmaip0Ltam4Gv0vAeJSXG800Clh512xt5yEoRx-hdCBCwsG7i>

1. Open the Link

- Tap the above internal link in your android phone.
- It will launch the app page in Google Play Store.

2. Enable Internal App Sharing

If you get a message that the internal app sharing is turned off, follow these steps:

2.1. Access Play Store Settings

- Tap the **Google Play settings** hyperlink in the notification, which will take you to your settings.

2.2. Enable Developer Mode

- Click on **“About”**.
- Find **“Play Store version”** and tap it **repeatedly** until you see the message *“You are now a developer.”*

2.3. Enable Internal App Sharing

- Go back to the Play Store settings / General / Developer Options / Internal App Sharing
- Under **“Developer options”**, turn on **“Internal app sharing.”**
- Close Play store and go back to the link.

3. Install the App

- Return to the app link in the Play Store.
- You'll now see an **Install** button which you can tap.
- Confirm the prompt asking if you want to install an internally shared app.

4. Launch the App

- Once the app is downloaded, tap **Open** to start using it.

5. When asked: **Allow the app to access this device's location?**

- Tap **Allow** (allow the app to receive local weather forecast)

6. You will see **“Welcome to MotherHeat Alert”**.

Så här laddar du ner MotherHeat Alert med en Android-telefon

Följ dessa steg för att installera appen (v1.1.2) från följande länk:

<https://play.google.com/apps/test/RQJb-fWZvac/ahAO29uNRfcTdNQ4UplopGTq5-2COe7FL4pT63odlVmaip0Ltam4Gv0vAeJSXG800Clh512xt5yEoRx-hdCBCwsG7i>

1. Öppna länken

- Tryck på den interna länken ovan i din Android-telefon.
- Det kommer att öppna appsidan i Google Play Store.

2. Aktivera Intern App Sharing

Om du får ett meddelande om att intern appdelning är avstängd följer du dessa steg:

2.1. Gå till Play Butik-inställningar

- Tryck på hyperlänken för **Google Play-inställningar** i meddelandet, vilket tar dig till dina inställningar.

2.2. Aktivera utvecklarläget

- Klicka på **“Om”**.
- Hitta **“Version av Play Butik”** och tryck på den flera gånger tills du ser meddelandet *“Du är nu en utvecklare”*

2.3. Aktivera Internal Appdelning

- Gå tillbaka till Play Butik inställningar och väljer Allmänt / Utvecklarnalternativ
- Inom **“Utvecklarnalternativ”**, aktivera **“Intern appdelning.”**
- Stänga Play Butiken och gå tillbaka till länken.

3. Installera Appen

- Klicka på länken på din telefon
- Du ser nu en **Installera-knapp** som du ska trycka på.
- Bekräfta frågan om du vill installera en Intern delad app.

4. Starta appen

- När appen har laddats ner, trycka på **”Öppna”** för att börja använda den.

5. På frågan: Tillåt appen att komma åt enhetens plats?

Tryck på **Tillåt** (tillåt att appen tar emot lokal väderprognos)

6. Du kommer att se **“Välkommen till MotherHeat Alert”**.

7.3 Annex C: Guidance document for iPhones

Because of the online recruitment of the cohort in Sweden, a guidance document on how to download, install and use the MotherHeat Alert app was shared with implementers in Sweden. The instructions are also incorporated in the online recruitment for cohort participants. The guidance document is available for iPhones and Android phones (Annex B).

How to Download the MotherHeat Alert Using iPhone

Follow these two steps:

1. Install TestFlight

Download and install the TestFlight app from the App Store:

<https://apps.apple.com/app/testflight/id899247664>

2. Join the Beta Test

After installing TestFlight, tap this link on your iPhone:

<https://testflight.apple.com/join/8UvP8gPA>

You will be redirected to the MotherHeat Alert app in TestFlight, where you can:

- a. Accept the invitation
- b. Install the app
- c. Start testing

TestFlight

Beta testing made simple

173 RATINGS

4.6

★★★★★

AGE

4+

Years Old

CHART

No. 3

Developer Tools

DEVELOPER

Apple

LANGUAGE

EN

+ 32 More

SIZE

4,7

MB

Så här laddar du ner MotherHeat Alert med iPhone

Följ dessa två steg:

1. Installera TestFlight

Ladda ner och installera TestFlight-appen från App Store:

<https://apps.apple.com/app/testflight/id899247664>

2. Gå med i Betatestet

När du har installerat TestFlight, trycker du på den här länken på din iPhone:

<https://testflight.apple.com/join/8UvP8gPA>

Du kommer att omdirigeras till MotherHeat Alert-appen i TestFlight, där du kan:

- a. Acceptera inbjudan
- b. Installera appen
- c. Börja testa

The screenshot shows the TestFlight app page on the App Store. It features the app icon (a blue square with a white propeller), the title "TestFlight", and the subtitle "Beta testing made simple". Below the icon is a green download icon. The page is divided into several sections: "173 RATINGS" with a 4.6 star rating, "AGE" with a 4+ rating, "CHART" with a No. 3 ranking, "DEVELOPER" with the Apple logo, "LANGUAGE" with EN and + 32 More, and "SIZE" with 4,7 MB.

173 RATINGS	AGE	CHART	DEVELOPER	LANGUAGE	SIZE
4.6 ★★★★★	4+ Years Old	No. 3 Developer Tools	Apple	EN + 32 More	4,7 MB